

ACOUSTIC REMOTE SENSING OF WIND WAVE
DIRECTIONAL PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

A Marsh McBirney MODEL MMI-555 was moored for a period of 21 days in the vicinity of Ambrose Tower, N.Y. close to a special prototype bottom mounted 300kHz Ametek Straza acoustic Doppler current profiler. The MMI-555 was operated in the burst mode taking 60 samples at 1-second intervals, each hour. Variances of the horizontal water velocities, measured by the MMI-555 and rotated into the directions of the Ametek beams, are compared to standard deviations of water velocities measured on the Ametek beams in bins near the MMI-555 depth. This paper provides further evidence in support of the authors previously stated hypothesis that directional waveheight spectra can be estimated from acoustic Doppler measurements.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of current profiling using acoustic Doppler measurements made its published debut in 1973 (Emmanuel and Mandics, 1973). In 1979, two papers were published describing shipboard mounted current profiling instruments (Rowe and Young, 1979; Peynaud and Pijanowski, 1979). In 1981 an experiment in real time current profiling using a bottom mounted upward looking acoustic Doppler profiler was published (Williams et al., 1981). From that time on, numerous publications have discussed the theory, instruments, and experiments associated with acoustic Doppler current profiling.

The oceanographic community has now largely changed from skepticism to acceptance of acoustic Doppler current profiling. This paper deals with a possible expansion of acoustic Doppler measurements to include the role of inferring directional wave information from measurements of the fluctuating subsurface current fields associated with surface gravity waves (Huff and Williams, 1986).

It is generally accepted that point measurements of horizontal orthogonal current components can be processed to yield an estimate of the one dimensional surface wave spectrum. Inclusion of simultaneous pressure measurements provides the information to resolve the 180 degree ambiguity in propagation direction and thereby yield directional wave spectra (Nagata, 1964; Bowden and White, 1966). This paper presents evidence that a suitably modified acoustic Doppler current profiler can provide the requisite information to estimate the directional spectrum of surface gravity waves.

DISCUSSION

Figure 1 illustrates a conceptual scheme for obtaining directional wave information via acoustic Doppler current profiler measurements. Spectra of the radial (parallel to the acoustic beam) current fluctuations in any beam, close to but not intersecting the surface, can be transformed into a one dimensional wave spectrum by making use of the relationships between surface waves and their associated subsurface orbital particle motion. In order to resolve the 180 degree ambiguity in propagation direction one must consider bins along a beam as comprising an array.

Phase of a given wave frequency in one element (bin) of the array relative to another element of the array yields the information necessary to resolve the directional ambiguity. For the higher frequencies, relative phase can be obtained between several successive near surface elements of the array. At that location the orbital particle motion of the higher frequency waves will be large compared to the measurement noise. For lower frequency waves it will be necessary to determine the relative phase between array elements which are more widely spaced. However, since lower frequencies attenuate slower with depth, their orbital particle motions will also be large compared to the measurement noise.

FIGURE 1 Conceptual Schematic for Obtaining Wave Information from Acoustic Doppler Current Profiles.

The principle is straightforward: determine the spectrum and propagation direction of the wave field in each of two orthogonal planes; then combine components to yield a composite wave variance and direction as a function of frequency. A test of this concept, however, is not so simple because it requires access to information not generally available from acoustic Doppler profilers. Over an extended time interval one must have the velocity estimates from each bin of each beam for each of numerous pulses, which must be closely spaced in time.

Lacking such data to fully test the concept, a review was conducted of the acoustic Doppler current profile data sets held by the National Ocean Service of NOAA to determine the extent to which any might be employed in partial testing of the concept. The data set taken at Ambrose Tower, N.Y. in the fall of 1983 with a specially modified Ametek Straza DCP4400 was determined to be applicable for this purpose. There have been significant improvements in instruments since 1983, yet the Ambrose Tower experiment was unique in that the prototype real time system reported standard deviations of velocity measurements in six minute intervals, as well as the mean of the observations in that interval. This data set falls short of ideal for testing the concept because the data for each bin of each beam yields no information as to how the variance was partitioned (Huff et al., 1986).

The Ambrose Tower data was, however, adequate for the purpose of this paper. The subset of acoustic Doppler current profile data taken in conjunction with burst sampled data from a MMI-555 moored by NOAA's Ocean Systems Division

as part of their Ambrose Tower Sea Truth Experiment (Magnell, 1984), provided the inputs for the analyses discussed in this paper.

FIGURE 2 Doppler Profiler Bin Numbers and MMI-555 Mooring for the Fall 1983 Sea Truth Experiment.

Figure 2 illustrates multiple bins on one of the four Ametek Straza beams and the subsurface mooring used to position the MMI-555 several meters below the sea surface. The MMI-555 was programmed such that on each hour, 60 samples were taken at one second intervals. These data were originally intended to support the estimation of velocity S/N during the sea truth experiment. Each hour's samples of X and Y velocity components were combined to investigate variance in the subsurface flow field and determine how it varied over the period of acoustic Doppler current profile data discussed in the paper. Figure 3 presents temporal changes of the variance in the subsurface horizontal flow field measured by the MMI-555.

Using each hour's burst sampled data, a vector component of current was computed for each three degrees of magnetic orientation from north around to south. The variances in each of these time series were computed and tested for the orientation with maximum variance. In this manner an estimate was made of the most energetic plane in the wave field. The results

FIGURE 3 Temporal Changes in the Variance of the MMI-555 Burst Current Measurements.

of this procedure are shown in figure 4, which presents a time series of the most energetic plane of the subsurface horizontal flow field measured by the MMI-555.

FIGURE 4 Temporal Changes in the Orientation of the Peak Energy Direction of the MMI-555 Burst Current Measurements.

Since sixty second record lengths are too short for reliable wave frequency analysis, autocorrelations for the North and East components of currents were computed in an attempt to obtain an indication of variability in the frequency content of the MMI-555 data. The North and East autocorrelations were then combined and normalized. Figure 5 is a waterfall presentation of the autocorrelations of the MMI-555 data. An autocorrelation value of

one was set graphically equal to the time interval of one day. If the frequency content of the wave field was constant then the waterfall presentation would be comprised of a repeating pattern without overlaps. Since figure 5 does not have that character, there must have been changes in the frequency content of the wave field.

Taken together, figures 3, 4, and 5 indicate that a typical range of coastal conditions occurred during the Ambrose Tower Sea Truth Experiment. Therefore, any conclusions drawn from this data set are unlikely to depend on any unique combination of period, amplitude or direction of the waves.

There is a lower limit on the uncertainty of a single ping velocity estimation which is dependant on system design parameters (Theriault, 1983; Christensen, 1983). This residual uncertainty causes the standard deviations reported by the Ametek to have a positive bias which was removed prior to comparisons with the MMI-555.

Each of the four Ametek beams was inclined from vertical by 30 degrees and separated in azimuth by 90 degrees. First consider an orthogonal pair of the beams, one of which is oriented in the same direction of a propagating surface gravity wave. The radial (parallel to the beam) velocity component sensed on that beam will be comprised partially of the vertical and horizontal components of the orbital particle motion. The variance in a bin on that beam will have contributions from the variance of both the vertical and horizontal [$\cos^2(30) \cdot \text{vertical variance} + \sin^2(30) \cdot \text{horizontal variance}$]. Bins on the orthogonal beam (perpendicular to the propagation direction of the surface gravity wave) will have a variance comprised only of the variance of the vertical component [$\cos^2(30) \cdot \text{vertical variance}$]. The beam geometry of the acoustic transducer causes the vertical component of the flow field to appear equally in all beams. If the surface gravity wave is propagating at any arbitrary angle relative to the pair of orthogonal axes then the sum of variance on the two beams is [$2 \cdot \cos^2(30) \cdot \text{vertical variance} + \sin^2(30) \cdot \text{horizontal variance}$]. The total variance in a bin on the four Ametek beams is therefore [$3 \cdot \text{vertical variance} + 0.5 \cdot \text{horizontal variance}$]. While the total variances in a two axis of the MMI-555 located at the same elevation as the Ametek bin is [$1 \cdot \text{horizontal variance}$]. If the surface gravity wave is a deep water wave and the bin in question is close to the surface then the vertical and horizontal orbital velocities are essentially equal and the ratio of the 4 beam total variance in the Ametek bin to the 2 axes total variance in the MMI-555 is 3.5.

FIGURE 5 Temporal Patterns in the Autocorrelations of MMI-555 Burst Current Measurements.

FIGURE 6 The Average Ratio between the Ametek Variances and the MMI-555 variances.

Figure 6 illustrates the average ratio between the total Ametek variance (summed over the 4 Ametek beams) and the total MMI-555 variance (summed over the 2 MMI-555 axes) for several Ametek bins. Figure 2 indicates that the MMI-555 data were acquired close to the same elevation above the bottom as that of Ametek bin 12. The ratios shown in figure 6 for bins 12 and 13 are comparable to the expected value of 3.5.

Figure 7 was developed by computing the hourly burst sample variances for different directions and then summing those variances to determine total variance in the 21 day sequence of MMI-555 data. The 21 day total variance is maximum for a rotation of 50 degrees clockwise from magnetic north. The maximum of figure 7 is located 20 degrees clockwise from the plane containing beams 1 and 2 (1/2 plane) of the bottom mounted Ametek.

FIGURE 7 21 Day Total Variance in Different Vector Projections of the MMI-555 Burst Current Measurements.

FIGURE 8 Average Ratio of Variances in the Ametek Beams 1 and 2 as Compared to the Variances in Different Vector Projections of the MMI-555 Burst Current Measurements.

FIGURE 9 Average Ratio of Variances in the Ametek Beams 3 and 4 as Compared to the Variances in Different Vector Projections of the MMI-555 Burst Current Measurements.

Figures 8 and 9 present the bin 12 and bin 14 ratios of the Ametek 21 day total variances in the 1/2 and 3/4 planes to MMI-555 21 day total variances for different directions. The patterns of the ratios for the Ametek 1/2 and 3/4 planes are very similar. They peak in the vicinity of 50 degree clockwise rotation. Figure 10 illustrates the zero time lag correlation coefficient between the time series variance of rotated vector projections of the MMI-555 data and the time series variance of bin 12 Ametek data for the 1/2 and 3/4 beam planes. Both planes of the Ametek show a pronounced increase in correlation with the MMI-555 vector projection of approximately 50 degrees clockwise from north.

Since the waves at Ambrose Tower were predominately deep water in nature, the horizontal and vertical components of the orbital motion were of comparable amplitude in the Ametek bins near the surface. The time history of variances in the vertical component of the orbital motion should, therefore, correspond closely to the time history of the variance in the horizontal component of the orbital motion oriented 50 degrees clockwise from magnetic north. This result follows from figure 7 which showed that the 21 day total variance in the time series of the 50 degree clockwise from north projection of the MMI-555 contained more than 2.5 times the 21 day total variance contained in the time series for the MMI-555 vector projection with the least 21 day total variance.

FIGURE 10 Correlations Between 21 Day Time Series of Variance in the two Ametek Measurement Planes and 21 Day Time Series of Variance in Different Projections of the MMI-555 Burst Current Measurements.

CONCLUSIONS

Since the Ametek, due to its beam geometry, is six times more sensitive to the variance associated with the vertical component of the flow field than to the variance associated with the horizontal component, it is not surprising that the curves in figures 8, 9, and 10 peak at the same rotation of the MMI-555 as did figure 7 and not at the physical orientation of the Ametek measurement planes.

A large common mode signal is present in the four Ametek beams because the beams respond equally to the vertical component of the subsurface flow field. The horizontal component of velocity from a four beam acoustic Doppler profiler is determined by subtracting the velocity estimates made on opposing pairs of beams. This subtraction removes the common mode vertical velocity components in the individual beams. Similarly, taking the difference between variances in an orthogonal pair of the Ametek beams will remove the common mode vertical component variance and thereby yield the difference between variances in orthogonal components of the horizontal flow field. In an four beam acoustic Doppler profiler specifically designed for wave current measurement, one beam would be directed vertically while the other three would be inclined by 30 to 45 degrees and separated in azimuth by 120 degrees. By this means, the vertical component of orbital particle motion could be independently determined and its variance removed from each beam. As a result of the vertical cosine response function of a MMI-555, its orthogonal components contain negligible common mode variances due to the

vertical components of the subsurface flow field. A similar differencing operation performed on the MMI-555 data would clearly yield the difference between the orthogonal components of the horizontal flow field measured by the MMI-555.

FIGURE 11 Correlation Between 21 Day Time Series of the Difference in Variance Between the two Ametek Measurement Planes and 21 Day Time Series of the Difference in Variance Between Two Orthogonal Projections of the MMI-555 Burst Current Measurements.

Figure 11 illustrates the zero time lag correlation between a 21 day time series of the difference in variance between the two Ametek measurement planes and 21 day time series of the differences in variances between rotated orthogonal components of the MMI-555 data. The curves in figure 11 have their maximum at a rotation of approximately 30 degrees clockwise from magnetic north. The curves peak when the MMI-555 data are mathematically rotated into axes which are parallel to the physical orientation of the Ametek.

Figure 11 demonstrates that after influence of the vertical flow field components is removed from the Ametek variances, the remaining Ametek variances have an azimuthal character which is comparable to that of the MMI-555.

SUMMARY

Wave measurement was not considered in the original design of the prototype system deployed at Ambrose Tower and consequently the Ambrose Tower data set has definite limitations for testing the concept of measuring directional wave properties. The primary limitations derive from the transducer geometry and the type of velocity information stored.

The discussions in this paper do however provide evidence that the premise of estimating waves via acoustic Doppler current profile measurements is valid because the basic acoustic Doppler current profiler velocity estimates contain the required information for the determination of directional wave spectra.

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